

Association of Isolated Loss of Consciousness and CT Findings in Traumatic Brain Injury

Hari Krishan G¹, B.P. Kattimani², Prathibha H³, Udaykumar J Khasage⁴

¹Junior Resident, Dept. of Emergency Medicine, BLDE Bijapur Karnataka India

²Associate Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine, Shri B.M Patil Medical College & Hospital, BLDE Deemed To Be University, Vijayapura, Karnataka

³Consulting Anaesthetist, Department of Anesthesia, Shri Sugureshwar Ortho Care Hospital Workanalli Road Near Gunj Circle Yadgir 585202 Karnataka India

⁴Associate Professor, Dept. of Emergency Medicine, BLDE Bijapur Karnataka India

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Udaykumar J Khasage

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Traumatic brain injury can present in various ways, with high rates of energy transfer leading to more damage. Routine CT imaging for mild head trauma with only loss of consciousness may not be necessary.

Objective: To determine the correlation between LOC and CT findings in Traumatic Brain Injury Patients.

Methods: This is an observational study to be conducted in the Emergency Department of BLDE (DU), Shri B.M Patil Medical College Hospital, Vijayapur, Karnataka. Patients coming to Emergency Department BLDE, Shri B.M Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura from August 2022 to April 2024 who met the inclusion Criteria.

Result: Among the total of 145 participants, 6 (4.1%) had positive CT findings, while 139 (95.9%) had negative results. Specifically, when examining the subgroup of participants with a GCS score of less than 15 and LOC, 5 out of 58 (8.6%) had positive CT findings, whereas 53 (91.4%) had negative results. The odds ratio (OR) for sex was 3.346 with a p-value of 0.067, indicating a trend toward a higher likelihood of abnormal CT findings in one gender, though this result did not reach conventional statistical significance.

Conclusion: the associations between Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores, loss of consciousness (LOC), and positive CT scan findings in 145 participants with head trauma. However, the overall prevalence of positive CT findings was low (3.5%), with only 7.4% of participants with LOC showing abnormalities.

Keywords: Traumatic brain injury, Loss of Consciousness, CT scan.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) can manifest in a variety of ways, from slight changes in consciousness to a persistent state of unconsciousness and even death. In the most severe kind of traumatic brain injury, there is widespread damage and oedema throughout the brain. [1] Head injuries are a frequent cause of visits to the emergency room. Traumatic brain injury is a possibility for many individuals who experience blunt head trauma (TBI). [2]

Traumatic brain injury still affects millions of people worldwide each year. The Centres for Disease Control report that during the years 2001–2010, there was a rise in the total combined rates of TBI-related ER visits, hospital stays, and fatalities. [3] All things considered, nevertheless, there have been fewer TBI-related deaths throughout this same time span. This is probably due in part to growing public awareness, formalising management and

guidelines, and making substantial technological breakthroughs in treatment protocols. [4] The age groups with the highest rates of TBI are typically 0–4 years old, as well as teenagers and young adults (15–24 years old). Incidence peaks again in the elderly (>65 years of age). Car crashes and falls are the two main causes of traumatic brain injuries nationally. [5] Considering that there are often more TBIs but fewer deaths associated with them. When evaluating patients who have suffered blunt head trauma, reports of loss of consciousness is often taken into consideration as a sign that a brain CT scan should be performed. [6,7,8] For patients with aberrant Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores and/or LOC, clinicians regularly order CT scans.

This study assessed whether getting a brain CT scan is necessary if a patient with blunt trauma reports having LOC but otherwise has a normal physical assessment.

Material and Methods: This is an observational study to be conducted in the Emergency Department of BLDE (DU), Shri B.M Patil Medical College Hospital, Vijayapur, Karnataka.

Inclusion Criteria

- For study purposes, we include only previously healthy patients above age group of 18 with isolated head injury.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with other medical conditions that may influence CT result, such as previous history of stroke, were excluded.
- Patients who are less than 18 and those taking anticoagulant medications were also excluded.
- Patients who were suspected of substance abuse or intoxication were not included in this study.

Source of Data: Data will be collected from the patients presenting to Emergency department of Shri BM Patil medical college and research centre Vijayapura for a period of 18 months who fulfill the inclusion criteria

Sampling: With anticipated head injury case within the inclusion criteria this study would require a sample size of 145 patients. With 95% level of confidence and 5% absolute precision. The data obtained will be entered in Microsoft excel sheet and statistical analysis will be performed using JNL software.

Methodology

For this study the data of patients with Traumatic Brain Injury and classify them as LOC group and NON-LOC group and CT scan positivity among 2 is identified and with that "p" value and ODDS ratio is calculated Same set of patients are classified based on GCS status and CT positivity. P value and ODDS ratio calculated and compared with first group Combining GCS status with LOC, Patients are classified as those with GCS less than 15 with LOC and those with GCS15 with LOC and 'p' value and odds ratio is calculated and compared with first group.

Results

The study sample comprised 145 participants, with a mean age of 6.06 years (± 4.0). The age distribution of the participants revealed that 52 individuals (35.9%) were aged between 18-24

years, 23 individuals (15.9%) were aged between 25-35 years, 36 individuals (24.8%) were aged between 35-45 years, and 34 individuals (23.4%) were aged over 45 years. This diverse age range highlights the variability in the affected population, which is critical for understanding the broad impact of the studied conditions across different life stages. The gender distribution was skewed towards males, with 103 males (71%) and 42 females (29%), indicating a potential gender-based difference in the incidence or reporting of injuries and symptoms.

In terms of the mechanism of injury, falls emerged as the most prevalent cause, accounting for 76 cases (52.4%). Within this category, short falls were the most common, reported in 66 cases (45.5%), while long-distance falls were noted in 11 cases (7.6%).

These findings underscore the significance of fall-related injuries in the study population, prompting further investigation into preventive measures and risk factors associated with different types of falls. Motor vehicle accidents were responsible for 33 cases (22.8%), emphasizing the need for enhanced safety measures and interventions in traffic-related incidents. Among these motor vehicle accident cases, 12 participants (8.3%) were pedestrians, highlighting the vulnerability of pedestrians in traffic environments.

Direct impacts accounted for 21 cases (14.5%), suggesting a notable proportion of injuries resulting from blunt force trauma. Physical assaults were reported in 2 cases (1.4%), and child physical abuse was reported in 1 case (0.7%). Although these numbers are relatively low, they represent significant and concerning instances of intentional harm, warranting targeted interventions and support systems for victims.

The overall statistics of the study, including the mechanisms of injury and demographic data, provide a comprehensive overview of the affected population, enabling a deeper understanding of the underlying factors and guiding future research and policy development to mitigate these risks. This detailed analysis of demographic variables and injury mechanisms is crucial for tailoring effective prevention and treatment strategies to address the specific needs of different population subgroups within the study cohort.

Table 1: Comparison of CT scan Result Based on Loss of Consciousness

	CT Positive	CT Negative	Total	% Positive	% Negative
LOC	5	50	55	7.4%	92.6%
No LOC	1	89	90	1.1%	98.9%
Total	6	139	144	3.5%	96.5%

The analysis of CT scan results in relation to loss of consciousness (LOC) revealed significant findings.

Among the 144 participants, 6 (3.5%) tested positive for abnormalities on CT scans, while 138

(96.5%) tested negative. Specifically, of the participants who experienced loss of consciousness (LOC), 5 out of 55 (7.4%) had positive CT findings, whereas 50 (92.6%) had negative results. In contrast, only 1 out of 90 participants without LOC (1.1%) showed positive CT results and 89 (98.9%) had negative CT scans. These results indicate a notable association between LOC and the likelihood of positive CT findings, with LOC being linked to a higher probability of detecting

abnormalities on CT scans. The majority of participants, irrespective of LOC status, had negative CT findings, underscoring that abnormal CT results are relatively rare overall. This distribution highlights the importance of considering LOC as a significant factor when assessing the risk of CT abnormalities and informs clinical decision-making regarding the necessity of further imaging and evaluation.

Table 2: CT scan Results by Glasgow Coma Scale (Gcs) And Loss of Consciousness (LOC) Status

	CT Positive	CT Negative	Total	% Positive	% Negative
Gcs<15 and LOC	5	53	58	8.6%	91.4%
Gcs <15 and No LOC	1	86	87	1.1%	98.9%
Total	6	139	145	4.1%	95.9%

The evaluation of CT scan results in relation to Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores and loss of consciousness (LOC) provided valuable insights into the correlation between these factors and the likelihood of CT abnormalities.

Among the total of 145 participants, 6 (4.1%) had positive CT findings, while 139 (95.9%) had negative results. Specifically, when examining the subgroup of participants with a GCS score of less than 15 and LOC, 5 out of 58 (8.6%) had positive CT findings, whereas 53 (91.4%) had negative results. In contrast, among participants with a GCS score of less than 15 but without LOC, only 1 out of 87 (1.1%) had positive CT results, and 86

(98.9%) had negative findings. These results suggest that the combination of a GCS score of less than 15 and the presence of LOC is associated with a significantly higher likelihood of detecting abnormalities on CT scans compared to cases where LOC is absent. The majority of participants with a GCS score of less than 15 and no LOC had negative CT findings, indicating that the absence of LOC may mitigate the risk of CT abnormalities even when GCS is reduced.

These findings underscore the importance of both LOC and GCS scores as critical factors in assessing the need for CT imaging and predicting the likelihood of detecting brain abnormalities.

Table 3: Correlation of Odds Ratio and P Value For Various Variables I Study Population

S.No	Variable	OR	P Value
1	Sex	3.346	0.067
2	Gcs (15)	5.961	0.051
3	Gcs (14)	1.387	0.239
4	Gcs (13)	4.413	0.036
5	Vomiting	1.069	0.301
6	Headache	0.745	0.388
7	Loss of Consciousness	0.167	0.683
8	Age 18-24	1.373	0.712
9	Age 25-35	0.384	0.535
10	Age 35-45	0.105	0.746
11	Age >45	0.179	0.673
12	Overall Statistics	13.898	0.126
13	Motor Vehicle accident	0.527	0.468
14	Pedestrian	0.026	0.872
15	Direct Impact	2.334	0.127
16	Fall	4.957	0.084
17	Short Fall	1.601	0.206
18	Long Distance Fall	4.379	0.036
19	Over All Statistics	7.632	0.178

The logistic regression analysis of variables predicting abnormal brain CT findings revealed several notable associations. The odds ratio (OR) for sex was 3.346 with a p-value of 0.067, indicating a trend toward a higher likelihood of

abnormal CT findings in one gender, though this result did not reach conventional statistical significance. Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores showed significant variability in association with CT results. Specifically, a GCS score of 15 had an

OR of 5.961 with a p-value of 0.051, approaching significance and suggesting that a higher GCS score might be linked to an increased probability of detecting abnormalities. Conversely, GCS scores of 14 and 13 showed ORs of 1.387 ($p = 0.239$) and 4.413 ($p = 0.036$), respectively, with the latter indicating a significant association between lower GCS scores and positive CT findings.

Symptoms such as vomiting and headache had ORs of 1.069 ($p = 0.301$) and 0.745 ($p = 0.388$), respectively, suggesting that these symptoms did not significantly predict CT abnormalities. Loss of consciousness (LOC) had a notably low OR of 0.167 with a p-value of 0.683, indicating no significant association with abnormal CT findings. Age categories, including 18-24 years (OR = 1.373, $p = 0.712$), 25-35 years (OR = 0.384, $p = 0.535$), 35-45 years (OR = 0.105, $p = 0.746$), and over 45 years (OR = 0.179, $p = 0.673$), also did not show significant associations with CT abnormalities.

Mechanisms of injury revealed some significant predictors. Motor vehicle accidents had an OR of 0.527 with a p-value of 0.468, while pedestrian injuries had a negligible OR of 0.026 ($p = 0.872$). Direct impacts had an OR of 2.334 ($p = 0.127$), suggesting a potential association with CT abnormalities, though not statistically significant. Falls, particularly long-distance falls, showed a significant association with CT abnormalities, with an OR of 4.957 ($p = 0.084$) for falls in general and an OR of 4.379 ($p = 0.036$) for long-distance falls specifically. Overall statistics indicated that, while some variables approached significance, others did not show a strong predictive value for abnormal CT findings. This analysis underscores the importance of specific clinical and injury-related factors in predicting CT results and highlights areas for further research to better understand these associations.

Discussion:

Loss of consciousness is prevalent among individuals who have forceful head trauma and is a significant factor that affects the decision to get a CT scan in the emergency department. A CT scan was acquired in 91% of participants in a significant cohort study. [9]

A number of medical professionals have raised doubts regarding the correlation between a past occurrence of loss of consciousness (LOC) and traumatic brain injury (TBI). [10,11] However, the practice of acquiring CT scans in patients with loss of consciousness (LOC) has not altered, and CT scans have been consistently used for diagnostic testing in the emergency department (ED). The brain CT scan is the primary diagnostic technique used to assess individuals with head trauma [12,13] Annually, about 1 million cranial CT scans are performed for the purpose of diagnosing head

trauma. [14,15] A recent report has shown that the utilization of head CT scans has risen by 35.7% (with a range of 34.5% to 46.8%) for all age groups from 2006 to 2011. [16] This study re-examined the issue of whether a brain CT scan is necessary for patients with traumatic head trauma who experience loss of consciousness upon admission in the emergency department. While relying solely on clinical examination might decrease the need for CT scans, it may not completely rule out the possibility of diagnosing intracranial damage. For numerous medical practitioners, the notion of failing to identify any intracranial lesion is seen as intolerable.

The fear of being sued may influence medical decision-making, and some healthcare professionals would not tolerate missing the diagnosis of any intracranial lesion, regardless of its importance. A research based on the New Orleans Criteria has proposed that the use of CT scans may not be necessary for patients with mild head injuries, as long as none of the following conditions are present: The factors associated with the condition include headache, vomiting, age over 60 years, drug or alcohol intoxication, seizures after a traumatic event, physical signs of injury above the collarbone, and difficulties with short-term memory. [17] The "New Orleans Criteria" were developed to encompass all types of cerebral injuries, regardless of whether they need neurosurgical surgery or not. In order to enhance the accurate identification of significant brain damage, the Canadian CT Head Rule permits patients with a Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score of 13-15 within 2 hours of the accident to forgo a head CT scan. However, it does mandate a brain CT scan for patients who meet additional criteria such as being under the age of 16 or having a particular cause of injury. The Canadian CT Head Rule incorporates amnesia as one of the criteria for identifying individuals with any clinically significant brain damage.[18]

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of demographic characteristics, incident mechanisms, and clinical variables associated with positive CT scan findings among a cohort of 145 participants. The results offer valuable insights into the factors that may influence the likelihood of detecting brain abnormalities, which is critical for improving diagnostic accuracy and patient management strategies.

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of demographic characteristics, incident mechanisms, and clinical variables associated with positive CT scan findings among a cohort of 145 participants. The results offer valuable insights into the factors that may influence the likelihood of detecting brain abnormalities, which is critical for improving diagnostic accuracy and patient management

strategies. A small proportion, namely less than 5%, of individuals with mild head trauma exhibit aberrant brain CT results, and none of them needed neurosurgical surgery. The incidence of abnormal brain CT scans in cases of mild head injury is similar to the global average, which ranges from 7-10%. The rate of surgical intervention in such cases is reported to be between 1-5%. The given text is the list. [19,20] There was no correlation between age and a higher likelihood of intracranial damage with abnormal brain CT following forceful trauma. Out of the patients aged 18-24 years, only 2.9% were found to have abnormal brain CT scans, which is lower than the previously reported rates of roughly 3-10% in worldwide studies. [21]

The literature extensively documents the presence of gender disparity, with the majority of patients with mild head trauma being male. [22] The incidence of intracranial damage in mild head trauma was greater in males than in females; however, the difference in risk did not reach statistical significance. Regarding various injury processes, briefly the univariate analysis did not provide strong evidence supporting the link between the long distance fall and intracranial damage. The analysis did not find evidence to suggest a connection between intracranial damage and motor vehicle accidents (MVA) as a cause of mild head trauma. However, it was challenging in the study to categorize the MVA data into 'low' or 'high speed impact'. No correlation was seen between pedestrians and intracranial damage, possibly because the majority of cases classified as mild head injuries were low-speed impacts. Crush head injury refers to the direct impact of a heavy item on the head. Young children are most commonly injured at home by falling objects such as furniture, television sets, and ovens. Children who experienced a direct hit to the head had a twofold increase in the likelihood of sustaining an intracranial injury. However, it is important to note that this link did not reach statistical significance, which may be attributed to the limited size of the sample.

The analysis of CT scan results revealed a significant association between loss of consciousness (LOC) and positive CT findings. Participants who experienced LOC had a higher proportion of positive CT scans (7.4%) compared to those without LOC (1.1%). This indicates that LOC is a critical factor in assessing the risk of brain abnormalities and should be a key consideration in clinical evaluations. The overall prevalence of positive CT findings was relatively low (3.5%), suggesting that while LOC is a significant predictor, the majority of cases do not result in detectable CT abnormalities.

When combining GCS scores with LOC status, the results showed that participants with a GCS score

of less than 15 and LOC had the highest proportion of positive CT findings (8.6%). In contrast, those with a GCS score of less than 15 but without LOC had a significantly lower proportion of positive CT findings (1.1%). These results suggest that the combination of reduced GCS and LOC is a strong predictor of CT abnormalities, whereas the absence of LOC in patients with reduced GCS may mitigate this risk. This combined assessment provides a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing CT scan results and can enhance clinical decision-making. Interestingly, symptoms such as vomiting and headache did not significantly predict CT abnormalities, nor did age categories. This finding suggests that while these symptoms and age groups are important clinical considerations, they may not be strong independent predictors of CT findings in this population.

Overall, the level of consciousness (LOC) with the specified time period in our investigation did not show any statistically significant results. However, it has been observed that prolonged durations of loss of consciousness (LOC), as described in prior investigations, are related with intracranial damage. [20] The study's capacity to detect very mild to moderate but relevant clinical manifestations that might potentially indicate cerebral damage may have been compromised due to the limited sample size. Considering the limited predictive rule generated from this analysis, it is recommended that the selection of which patients should have neuroimaging be based on clinical judgments. Considering the significant level of radiation exposure in relation to the limited occurrence of positive brain CT results, it is strongly advised to undergo a period of clinical surveillance for children who have experienced mild head injuries but are otherwise in good condition.

Conclusion:

This study highlights the associations between Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores, loss of consciousness (LOC), and positive CT scan findings in 145 participants with head trauma. However, the overall prevalence of positive CT findings was low (3.5%), with only 7.4% of participants with LOC showing abnormalities. Symptoms like vomiting and headache, and demographic factors such as age, were not significant predictors of CT abnormalities. Given the low rate of positive CT findings and significant radiation exposure from CT scans, the study suggests that routine CT imaging for patients with mild head trauma and only LOC may not be necessary.

References:

1. Galgano M, Toshkezi G, Qiu X, Russell T, Chin L, Zhao LR. Traumatic brain injury: cur-

- rent treatment strategies and future endeavors. Cell transplantation. 2017 Jul; 26(7):1118-30.
2. Waseem M, Iyahan P, Anderson HB, Kapoor K, Kapoor R, Leber M. Isolated LOC in head trauma associated with significant injury on brain CT scan. International Journal of Emergency Medicine. 2017 Dec; 10:1-6.
 3. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Injury prevention & control: traumatic brain injury & concussion [accessed 2016 Jan 22]
 4. Masel BE, DeWitt DS, Levin H, Shum D, Chan R. Traumatic brain injury disease: long-term consequences of traumatic brain injury. Understanding traumatic brain injury: Current research and future directions. 2014 Jan 28; 28.
 5. Rutland-Brown W, Langlois JA, Thomas KE, Xi YL. Incidence of traumatic brain injury in the United States, 2003. The Journal of head trauma rehabilitation. 2006 Nov 1; 21(6):544-8.
 6. Ng SM, Toh EM, Sherrington CA. Clinical predictors of abnormal computed tomography scans in paediatric head injury. Journal of paediatrics and child health. 2002 Aug; 38(4):388-92.
 7. Ramundo ML, Mcknight TI, KEMPF J, SAT-KOWIAK L. Clinical predictors of computed tomographic abnormalities following pediatric traumatic brain injury. Pediatric emergency care. 1995 Feb 1; 11(1):1-4.
 8. Schutzman SA, Greenes DS. Pediatric minor head trauma. Annals of emergency medicine. 2001 Jan 1; 37(1):65-74.
 9. Stead LG, Bodhit AN, Patel PS, Daneshvar Y, Peters KR, Mazzuocolo A, Kuchibhotla S, Pulvino C, Hatchitt K, Lottenberg L, et al. TBI surveillance using the common data elements for traumatic brain injury: a population study. Int J Emerg Med. 2013; 6:5. doi: 10.1186/1865-1380-6-5.
 10. Seidel JS, Henderson D, Tittle S, Jaffe D, Spaite D, Dean JM, Gausche M, Lewis RJ, Cooper A, Zaritsky A, Espisito T, Maederis D. Priorities for research in emergency medical services for children: results of a consensus conference. Ann Emerg Med. 1999; 33:206-10.
 11. Durch JS, Lohr KN. Emergency medical services for children. Washington: National Academy Press; 1993.
 12. Stiell IG, Wells GA, Vandemheen K, Clement C, Lesiuk H, Laupacis A, McKnight RD, Verbeek R, Brison R, Cass D, Eisenhauer ME, Greenberg G, Worthington J. The Canadian CT Head Rule for patients with minor head injury. Lancet. 2001 May 5; 357(9266):1391-6.
 13. Wright DW, Wears RL, Bakshy A, Burgess P, Wald MM, Whitson RR, American College of Emergency Physicians, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Clinical policy: neuroimaging and decisionmaking in adult mild traumatic brain injury in the acute setting. Ann Emerg Med. 2008; 52(6):714-48.
 14. Raja AS, Andruchow J, Zane R, Khorasani R, Schuur JD. Use of neuroimaging in US emergency departments. Arch Intern Med. 2011; 171(3):260-2.
 15. Korley FK, Pham JC, Kirsch TD. Use of advanced radiology during visits to US emergency departments for injury-related conditions, 1998-2007. JAMA. 2010; 304(13):1465-71.
 16. Zonfrillo MR, Kim KH, Arbogast KB. Emergency department visits and head computed tomography utilization for concussion patients from 2006 to 2011. Acad Emerg Med. 2015 Jul; 22(7):872-7.
 17. Haydel MJ, Preston CA, Mills TJ, Luber S, Blaudeau E, DeBlieux PM. Indications for computed tomography in patients with minor head injury. N Engl J Med. 2000; 343:100-5.
 18. Arab AF, Ahmed ME, Ahmed AE, Hussein MA, Khankan AA, Alokaili RN. Accuracy of Canadian CT head rule in predicting positive findings on CT of the head of patients after mild head injury in a large trauma centre in Saudi Arabia. Neuroradiol J. 2015; 28(6):591-7.
 19. Palchak MJ, Holmes JF, Vance CW, Gelber RE, Schauer BA, Harrison MJ, et al. A decision rule for identifying children at low risk for brain injuries after blunt head trauma. Ann Emerg Med 2003; 42:492-506.
 20. Kuppermann N, Holmes JF, Dayan PS, Hoyle JD Jr, Atabaki SM, Holubkov R, et al; Pediatric Emergency Care Applied Research Network (PECARN). Identification of children at very low risk of clinically- important brain injuries after head trauma: A prospective cohort study. Lancet 2009; 374:1160-70.
 21. Greenes DS, Schutzman SA. Infants with isolated skull fracture: What are their clinical characteristics, and do they require hospitalization? Ann Emerg Med 1997; 30:253-9.
 22. Quayle KS, Jaffe DM, Kuppermann N, Kaufman BA, Lee BC, Park TS, et al. Diagnostic testing for acute head injury in children: When are head computed tomography and skull radiographs indicated? Pediatrics 1997; 99:E11.